

QSAR with electrotopological state atom index. Part-V[†]. Anti-inflammatory activity of 7 α -halogenocorticosteroids and their derivatives

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The electrotopological state atom (ETSA) index is a structural descriptor encoding both electronic feature and topological environment of each skeletal atom of a molecule. The index has been projected to have potential to determine pharmacophore moieties of biologically active congeneric compounds. Quantitative structure activity relationship (QSAR) study of topical anti-inflammatory potency of 7 α -halogenocorticosteroids and their derivatives shows the importance of 3-keto, 20-keto and 11-hydroxy groups, 9-fluoro atom and 7-halogen groups in the mediation of the activity. This proves the diagnostic potential of ETSA schemes in identifying the pharmacophoric fragments. Again, use of indicator variables show that presence of 6,7-unsaturation and a methyl (β) group at C-16 position decrease the activity. QSAR involving physicochemical parameters reveals that the lipophilicity ($\log P$) and molar refractivity (MR) parameters are also important contributors to the activity.

The corticosteroids are adrenal cortical hormones having a cyclopentanoperhydrophenanthrene (steroid) nucleus and possess wide-spread biological activities including glucocorticoid and mineralocorticoid actions^{1,2}. The mineralocorticoids have effects on Na, K and fluid balance while glucocorticoid actions include carbohydrate, protein and fat metabolism, calcium metabolism and water excretion, apart from actions on cardiovascular system, skeletal muscle, central nervous system, lymphoid and blood cells, inflammatory response and immunological responses. Molecular mechanism of corticoid action in general is well established. Corticosteroids penetrate into cells and bind to a high affinity cytoplasmic receptor protein. The steroid receptor complex undergoes a structural change that allows its migration into the nucleus and binding to specific site on chromatin followed by transcription of specific m-RNA and regulation of protein synthesis.

Glucocorticosteroids and their metabolites were early recognized as possessing powerful anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties. Since the introduction of cortisone and hydrocortisone, anti-inflammatory steroids have remained an important and unreplaced drug class. Though not without adverse effects, natural and synthetic

glucocorticoid compounds have continued to be the drug of choice in various inflammatory disorders. The glucocorticoid receptor (GR) is a cytoplasmic protein of complex structure that is associated with various heat shock proteins (e.g. hsp 90)³. When activated by agonistic binding of the drug to the C-terminal region of GR, the GR-drug complex translocates to the nucleus and binds by its zinc finger region to the glucocorticoid response element of DNA, stimulating synthesis of anti-inflammatory proteins³. They exert anti-inflammatory action by a variety of mechanisms : (i) induction of lipocortins in macrophages leading to decreased production of prostaglandins, leukotrienes and platelet activating factor, (ii) negative regulator of gene for cytokines in macrophages, endothelial cells and lymphocytes leading to decreased production of IL-1, IL-2, IL-3, IL-6, TNF- α etc., (iii) decrease in products of action phase reactants from macrophages leading to interference in the complement functions, (iv) inhibition of IgE mediating histamine and LTC₄ release from basophils, leading to interference the antigen-antibody reaction⁴ etc. Comprehensive reviews dealing with structure-activity relationships of anti-inflammatory steroids involving Hansch

[†]For Parts I-IV, vide Refs. 9-12.

analysis, *de novo* analysis, principal component analysis, CoMFA analysis etc. have been published³. The results of these theoretical steroids are summarised here.

The introduction of a double bond at C1 leads to enhanced anti-inflammatory activity while that of hydroxyl group at the position leads to inactive compound. Introduction of a 2 α -fluoro group reduces the biological activity, but by contrast, 2-halogenation in $\Delta^{1,4}$ -3-ketocorticosteroids leads to highly potent compounds. Almost all active anti-inflammatory steroids have a carbonyl group at C3. The double bond between C4 and C5 position is important but not essential for anti-inflammatory activity. Polar substituents (such as hydroxy or oxo) in the 6 α -position decrease biological activity, whereas 6 α -substituted hydrophobic substituents (such as alkyl or halogens) tend to increase activity. 6 β -Substituents of any type and both 7 α - and 7 β -substituents impair biological activity. However, 6,7-difluoromethylene substituents can give rise to highly active compounds. Introduction of an 8(9)-double bond gives products of somewhat lower anti-inflammatory activity. The introduction of an 9 α -fluoro substituent alters the conformation of the entire steroid molecule and increases the activity and hydrogen bonding capacity of the 11 β -hydroxyl group. These changes influence receptor binding, protein binding and metabolic activity. Removal of the 19-angular methyl group reduces anti-inflammatory activity. However, if the removal of 19-angular methyl group is accompanied by aromatization of the A-ring, the compound retains activity. The C11 oxygen group is not essential for anti-inflammatory activity if enough other enhancing groups are present in the molecule. However, 11 α -hydroxy epimer of cortisol is inactive in glycogen deposition test. 9 α ,11 β -Dihalo steroids have useful anti-inflammatory activity which may be due to their conversion to the 11 β -hydroxy compounds. 12 α -Hydroxycorticosterone has 1/10th activity of cortisol in the glycogen deposition test. 12 α -Methyl-11-oxo-deoxycorticosterone is less active in the glycogen deposition test than the corresponding compound which lacks 12 α -methyl group. 15 α -Methyl group enhances anti-inflammatory activity while a 15 β -methyl group has little effect. 16 α -Hydroxyl group decreases activity while 16 α -methyl or 16 α -fluoro group enhances the activity. The 17 α -hydroxyl group is not essential for activity. The 17 α -halo compounds are of inferior activity. Ketalization of C-20 carbonyl group of corticosteroids retains biological activity. Reduction of cortisol to 21-deoxycortisol reduces activity. Oxidation of cortisol to 21-aldehyde retains activity. A steroid containing 21-carboxylic acid shows significant activity on skin, but no systemic action.

The present study is aimed at exploring QSAR of topi-

cal anti-inflammatory potency of some 7 α -halogeno corticosteroids⁵ with electrotopological state atom⁶⁻⁸ (ETSA) index which has been suggested as an important scheme capable of identifying atoms or fragments significantly influencing the activity. Additionally some physicochemical and indicator parameters were also used for the study.

ETSA index :

The ETSA index^{9,10} developed by Hall and Kier⁶⁻⁸ is an atom level descriptor encoding both the electronic character and topological environment of each skeletal atom in a molecule. It is derived from chemical graph theoretic approach and has two basic components : (i) intrinsic topological and electronic state of an atom and (ii) effect of the environment influencing the atom, considering differences in the intrinsic topological states of different atoms and topological distances among them which determine the magnitude of the interactions. The electrotopological states of atoms have been shown to bear relationships with relative electronrichness or ionicity of different atoms, their topological states (i.e. relative exposed or buried nature), and relative positions among different substituents or groups. Correlation also has been shown between electrotopological values with NMR shifts.

QSAR with ETSA index :

In our previous papers^{11,12} involving QSAR with ETSA index, estrogenic and progestagenic activities of steroidal compounds were considered. In the present effort, QSAR of anti-inflammatory activity of 7 α -halogeno corticosteroids⁵ and their derivatives with ETSA index have been explored. The anti-inflammatory activity dataset (Table 1) of the substituted 7 α -halogeno corticosteroids were taken from reference⁵. Along with 7 α -halogeno derivatives, three reference compounds (hydrocortisone, β -methasone velerate and β -methasone 17,21-dipropionate) were also included in the study. All 42 compounds considered in the present study contain twentyfive common atoms. The atoms of the molecules were numbered keeping serial numbers of the common atoms same in all the compounds (Fig. 1). The electrotopological states of the twentyfive common atoms of the fortytwo compounds were found out using a GW-BASIC program ELECTROL¹³ developed in this laboratory. The program uses, as input, only the connection table in the specified format along with intrinsic state values of different atoms. To the output file thus obtained, the biological activity data were introduced to make it ready for subsequent regression analysis. The program AUTOREG¹³ was used to correlate biological activity with ETSA index of different atoms and also to different combinations of them

Table 1. Topical anti-inflammatory activity and physicochemical parameters of substituted 7 α -halogeno corticosteroids and their derivatives

Compd. no.	Substitutions				BA (%)	Physicochemical parameters	
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	X	Obs.	log P	MR
1	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	-	H	63.00	2.24	126.28
2	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	-	H (6,7-dehydro)	51.00	1.92	127.40
3	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	-	Cl	84.00	2.31	130.92
4	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	-	Br	90.00	2.43	133.91
5	Cl	COCH ₂ CH ₃	-	H	50.00	2.59	115.55
6	Cl	COCH ₂ CH ₃	-	Cl	39.00	2.65	120.20
7	Cl	COCH ₂ CH ₃	-	Br	40.00	2.77	123.18
8	H	COCH ₂ CH ₃	-	Cl	13.00	2.13	115.44
9	OCOCH ₃	H	α -CH ₃	H	26.00	1.11	112.35
10	OCOCH ₃	H	α -CH ₃	H (6,7-dehydro)	29.00	0.79	113.46
11	OCOCH ₃	H	α -CH ₃	F	16.00	0.65	112.25
12	OCOCH ₃	H	α -CH ₃	Cl	81.00	1.17	116.99
13	OCOCH ₃	H	α -CH ₃	Br	94.00	1.29	119.97
14	OCOCH ₃	H	α -CH ₃	I	54.00	1.68	125.32
15	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	α -CH ₃	H	76.00	2.64	130.75
16	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	α -CH ₃	H (6,7-dehydro)	57.00	2.32	131.87
17	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	α -CH ₃	F	69.00	2.29	130.65
18	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	α -CH ₃	Cl	176.00	2.71	135.40
19	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	α -CH ₃	Br	186.00	2.83	138.38
20	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	α -CH ₃	I	103.00	3.22	143.73
21	Cl	COCH ₂ CH ₃	α -CH ₃	H	23.00	2.99	120.03
22	Cl	COCH ₂ CH ₃	α -CH ₃	Cl	17.00	3.05	124.67
23	OH	OH	α -CH ₃	Cl	8.00	0.94	107.84
24	OCOCH ₃	H	β -CH ₃	H	10.00	1.11	112.35
25	OCOCH ₃	H	β -CH ₃	H (6,7-dehydro)	4.00	0.79	113.46
26	OCOCH ₃	H	β -CH ₃	Cl	32.00	1.17	116.99
27	OCOCH ₃	H	β -CH ₃	Br	20.00	1.29	119.97
28	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	β -CH ₃	H	74.00	2.64	130.75
29	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	β -CH ₃	H (6,7-dehydro)	27.00	2.32	131.87
30	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	β -CH ₃	F	78.00	2.19	130.65
31	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	β -CH ₃	Cl	77.00	2.71	135.40
32	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	β -CH ₃	Br	120.00	2.83	138.38
33	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	β -CH ₃	I	35.00	3.22	143.73
34	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	=CH ₂	H	103.00	2.29	130.45
35	OCOCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	=CH ₂	Cl	139.00	2.35	135.10

(36-39)

(40)

(41-42)

	R ₁	R ₂	X	Obs	log P	MR
36	OCOCH ₃	-	H	91.00	1.11	121.44
37	OCOCH ₃	-	H (6,7-dehydro)	25.00	0.79	122.56
38	OCOCH ₃	-	Cl	18.00	1.17	126.09
39	OCOCH ₃	-	Br	124.00	1.29	129.07
40	-	-	-	3.00	1.04	102.03
41	H	CO(CH ₂) ₃ CH ₃	-	100.00	3.60	135.05
42	COCH ₂ CH ₃	COCH ₂ CH ₃	-	170.00	3.65	139.63

Table 2(a). Autocorrelation (*r*) among ETSA values of different atoms (*S_x* with *S_y*)

<i>x</i>	<i>y</i>											
	1	2	3	22	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	19
1	1.00	1.00	0.20	0.27	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.05	0.29	0.13	0.20
2		1.00	0.30	0.27	0.01	0.01	0.08	0.07	0.09	0.18	0.01	0.08
3			1.00	0.15	0.94	0.92	0.20	0.36	0.76	0.70	0.83	0.84
22				1.00	0.03	0.06	0.20	0.18	0.13	0.03	0.10	0.02
4					1.00	1.00	0.12	0.31	0.78	0.73	0.84	0.89
5						1.00	0.02	0.22	0.79	0.71	0.82	0.87
6							1.00	0.97	0.24	0.22	0.19	0.20
7								1.00	0.48	0.26	0.25	0.29
8									1.00	0.21	0.39	0.44
9										1.00	0.98	0.96
10											1.00	0.99
19												1.00

Table 2(b). Autocorrelation (*r*) among ETSA values of different atoms (*S_x* with *S_y*)

<i>x</i>	<i>y</i>												
	11	12	13	18	14	15	16	17	24	20	23	21	25
1		0.24	0.23	0.11	0.30	0.13	0.09	0.06	0.17	0.17	0.32	0.37	0.22
2		0.13	0.12	0.04	0.22	0.03	0.03	0.10	0.13	0.19	0.28	0.39	0.20
3		0.79	0.80	0.81	0.67	0.92	0.86	0.56	0.37	0.20	0.38	0.38	0.13
22	0.10	0.02	0.10	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.21	0.21	0.65	0.17	0.82	0.05	0.94
4		0.81	0.82	0.82	0.77	0.94	0.88	0.53	0.41	0.10	0.47	0.20	0.18
5		0.79	0.79	0.79	0.70	0.92	0.87	0.55	0.37	0.13	0.42	0.23	0.17
6		0.28	0.31	0.36	0.37	0.31	0.20	0.05	0.24	0.01	0.21	0.06	0.01
7		0.33	0.39	0.48	0.49	0.48	0.34	0.04	0.30	0.00	0.27	0.03	0.01
8		0.36	0.43	0.70	0.61	0.79	0.73	0.48	0.37	0.06	0.35	0.22	0.10
9		0.99	0.91	0.66	0.60	0.74	0.67	0.37	0.30	0.19	0.40	0.16	0.21
10	0.99	0.93	0.74	0.63	0.84	0.78	0.47	0.32	0.23	0.40	0.29	0.21	0.09
19	0.98	0.94	0.79	0.72	0.88	0.80	0.47	0.40	0.13	0.49	0.18	0.23	0.04
11	1.00	0.97	0.79	0.69	0.84	0.77	0.44	0.39	0.20	0.49	0.23	0.27	0.04
12		1.00	0.90	0.81	0.90	0.82	0.51	0.59	0.07	0.67	0.24	0.39	0.02
13			1.00	0.90	0.93	0.90	0.63	0.76	0.06	0.79	0.30	0.46	0.09
18				1.00	0.81	0.75	0.44	0.86	0.39	0.87	0.13	0.40	0.34
14					1.00	0.94	0.63	0.53	0.11	0.59	0.31	0.30	0.12
15						1.00	0.84	0.58	0.06	0.62	0.38	0.40	0.17
16							1.00	0.50	0.04	0.51	0.42	0.45	0.24
17								1.00	0.64	0.94	0.14	0.54	0.33
24									1.00	0.52	0.71	0.20	0.78
20										1.00	0.09	0.70	0.30
23											1.00	0.18	0.93
21												1.00	0.07
25													1.00

Fig. 1. General structure of 7 α -halogeno corticosteroids and their derivatives (the common atoms have been numbered 1 through 25).

to find the best univariate, bivariate and trivariate relations. For the bivariate (and trivariate) relations, only those with better statistical quality than the best univariate (bivariate) relation and predictor variables of which are not much autocorrelated ($r < 0.7$) were considered. Using the program RRR98¹³ regression constants with corresponding standard errors and various statistical parameters reflecting quality of the equations were found out.

The relations were improved further by using suitable indicator variables. Attempt was made also to derive relations involving physicochemical parameters [lipophilicity ($\log P$) and steric parameters (molar refractivity, MR)]¹⁴. The physicochemical parameters were calculated using the package Chem Draw Ultra version 5.0¹⁵ using best method option. A compound was considered as an outlier when the residual value exceeded twice the standard error of estimate (SEE) of the equation.

Results and Discussion

QSAR with ETSA index :

Among the univariate relations of the activity with ETSA parameters, the best relations involve atom nos. 22 (EV = 48.1%, $r = 0.703$), 23 (EV = 51.8%, $r = 0.728$) and 25 (EV = 47.5%, $r = 0.698$). Again autocorrelation study among the ETSA parameters (Tables 2a and 2b) shows that ETSA values of these three atoms are highly autocorrelated. Hence, a new parameter S_{C1} is defined as an average of ETSA values of atoms 22, 23 and 25 and the relation involving S_{C1} can explain 53.2% of the variance ($r = 0.737$) of the activity.

In the bivariate relations having better statistical quality than that of the best univariate relations, the atoms showing importance are 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12 and 19, apart from the atoms, 22, 23 and 25 ($r < 0.7$). Again, autocorrelation matrix shows that the atoms, 9, 10, 11, 12, 19 are highly autocorrelated and a new parameter S_{C2} is defined as an average of ETSA values of these atoms. Similarly, atoms 6 and 7 are also autocorrelated and a parameter S_{C3} is defined as an average of ETSA values of atoms 6 and 7. The bivariate relation involving S_{C1} and S_{C2} can explain 58.0% of the

variance ($R = 0.774$) while that involving S_{C1} and S_{C3} can explain 57.5% of the variance ($R = 0.771$). The trivariate relations do not show significant improvement in the statistical quality compared to the bivariate relations.

Table 3. Observed and calculated biological activity (log BA)

Compd. no.	Obs.	Calcd. ^a	Residual ^a	Calcd. ^b	Residual ^b
1	1.799	1.791	0.008	1.852	-0.052
2	1.708	1.578	0.129	1.722	-0.014
3	1.924	1.941	-0.017	2.014	-0.090
4	1.954	1.956	-0.002	2.095	-0.141
5	1.699	1.393	0.306	1.321	0.378
6	1.591	1.543	0.048	1.478	0.113
7	1.602	1.557	0.045	1.541	0.061
8	1.114	1.376	-0.262	1.454	-0.340
9	1.415	1.319	0.096	1.323	0.092
10	1.462	1.109	0.353	1.043	0.420
11	1.204	1.428	-0.224	1.174	0.031
12	1.908	1.469	0.439	1.517	0.392
13	1.973	1.484 ^c	0.489	1.654	0.319
14	1.732	1.490	0.242	1.888	-0.156
15	1.881	1.971	-0.090	1.894	-0.013
16	1.756	1.756	0.000	1.817	-0.061
17	1.839	2.080	-0.241	2.009	-0.171
18	2.246	2.121	0.124	2.045	0.200
19	2.270	2.136	0.134	2.105	0.164
20	2.013	2.142	-0.129	2.090	-0.771
21	1.362	1.572	-0.211	1.305	0.057
22	1.230	1.722 ^c	-0.492	1.452	-0.221
23	0.903	1.083	-0.180	1.104	-0.201
24	1.000	1.071	-0.071	1.082	-0.082
25	0.602	0.861	-0.259	0.802	-0.200
26	1.505	1.222	0.284	1.276	0.229
27	1.301	1.236	0.065	1.413	-0.112
28	1.869	1.723	0.146	1.653	0.217
29	1.431	1.509	-0.077	1.576	-0.145
30	1.892	1.832	0.060	1.793	0.099
31	1.886	1.873	0.013	1.804	0.082
32	2.079	1.888	0.191	1.864	0.215
33	1.544	1.895	-0.351	1.849	-0.305
34	2.013	1.936	0.076	2.002	0.011
35	2.143	2.086	0.057	2.166	-0.023
36	1.959	1.852	0.107	1.678	0.281
37	1.398	1.639	-0.241	1.398	0.000
38	1.255	1.777 ^c	-0.522	1.872 ^c	-0.617
39	2.093	1.792	0.302	2.009	0.085
40	0.477	0.821	-0.344	0.904	-0.427
41	2.000	1.918	0.082	2.046	-0.046
42	2.230	2.312	-0.082	2.184	0.046

^aAccording to eqn. (2).

^bAccording to eqn. (3).

^cCompound behaves as outlier.

Again incorporating indicator variables $I_{16\beta}$ (denoting presence or absence of methyl (β) group at C-16 position) and I_{9X} (denoting presence or absence of fluoro atom at C 9), the relations improved further and two of such relations are given below :

$$\log BA = 1.555S_{C1} - 0.691S_{C2} - 0.107^*S_{C3} - 0.234 I_{16\beta} - 17.317$$

(0.202) (0.252) (0.063) (0.094) (2.494)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{EV} = 64.8\%, \quad \text{CV} = 15.4\%, \quad R = 0.826, \\ \text{SEE} = 0.254, \quad F = 19.9 \quad (\text{df. } 4, 37), n = 42 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

log BA =

$$\begin{aligned} 1.652S_{C1} - 0.136S_{C3} + 0.632I_{9X} - 0.248I_{16\beta} - 18.590 \\ (0.193) \quad (0.058) \quad (0.190) \quad (0.090) \quad (2.385) \\ \text{EV} = 67.4\%, \text{CV} = 14.8\%, R = 0.840, \\ \text{SEE} = 0.244, F = 22.2 (\text{df. } 4, 37), n = 42 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The standard errors of the regression constants are indicated beneath the corresponding terms. The accepted equations have regression coefficients significant at 95% level unless superscripted with (*). The calculated values according to eqn. (2) are shown in Table 3. The variable S_{C1} signifies the importance of atoms 22 (3-keto group), 23 (20-keto) and 25 (11-hydroxy) groups. Again the variable S_{C2} actually signifies the importance of 9-fluoro atom. As the parameter S_{C2} bears negative coefficient and presence of 9-fluoro atom decreases the value of S_{C2} and thus presence of 9-fluoro atom increases the activity. The variable S_{C3} signifies the importance of 6 and 7 positions. Presence of 7-halogen group decreases the value of S_{C3} . Again, S_{C3} bears negative coefficients in eqn. (2), suggesting that the presence of 7-halo group increases activity. All these observations are in good agreement with the reports on SAR of these type of compounds obtained by different methods³. This proves the diagnostic potential of the ETSA scheme in identifying important atoms significantly influencing the activity.

QSAR with physicochemical parameters :

While correlating the biological activity with physicochemical parameters, lipophilicity (log P : EV = 27.1%, r = 0.536; for parabolic relation : EV = 28.9%, R = 0.568) and molar refractivity (MR : EV = 56.6%, r = 0.759) showed significant importance. However, the lipophilicity and steric parameters show some intercorrelation (r^2 = 0.558).

Incorporation of these parameters into equations involving ETSA parameters did not generate statistically acceptable equations because of intercorrelation between physicochemical and ETSA parameters. Further, incorporating indicator parameters $I_{16\beta}$, I_{9X} and $I_{6,7}$ (denoting presence or absence of unsaturation at 6,7-position) the following relation was obtained :

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{BA} = \\ 0.683 \log P - 0.208 (\log P)^2 + 0.039 \text{MR} - 0.241 I_{16\beta} + 0.815 I_{9X} - 0.232 I_{6,7} - 3.50 \\ (0.320) \quad (0.081) \quad (0.006) \quad (0.088) \quad (0.270) \quad (0.111) \quad (1.057) \\ \text{EV} = 69.6\%, \text{CV} = 14.3\%, R = 0.860, \\ \text{SEE} = 0.236, F = 16.6 (\text{df. } 6, 35), n = 42 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Though molar refractivity shows more importance than lipophilicity parameter and there is some intercorrelation among them, the latter has been retained considering its sig-

nificant coefficient (at 95% level) and that omission of this causes a substantial reduction in quality of the equations and makes some of the indicator variables insignificant. Further, omission of lipophilicity parameter may suppress the information on its contribution to the biological activity. Again removing one outlier (compound 38), the following relation was obtained :

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{BA} = \\ 0.618 \log P - 0.208 (\log P)^2 + 0.043 \text{MR} - 0.270 I_{16\beta} + 0.867 I_{9X} - 0.279 I_{6,7} - 3.910 \\ (0.287) \quad (0.072) \quad (0.053) \quad (0.079) \quad (0.242) \quad (0.100) \quad (0.967) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{EV} = 75.7\%, \text{CV} = 12.8\%, R = 0.890,$$

$$\text{SEE} = 0.211, F = 21.8 (\text{df. } 6, 34), n = 41 \quad (4)$$

The calculated values according to eqn. (3) are shown in Table 3. The equations suggest the importance of lipophilicity and molar refractivity parameters for the anti-inflammatory potency indicating the possibility of hydrophobic and dispersion interactions at the receptor site. The ideal lipophilicity is calculated to be 1.49 from eqn. (4). Again, a methyl group with β -orientation at C-16 position or the presence of 6,7-unsaturation decreases the activity, while the presence of 9-fluoro substitution increases activity.

Overview of QSAR :

The study shows that the equations involving ETSA parameters reveal the importance of different atoms of 7 α -halogenocorticosteroids for their anti-inflammatory activity : 3-keto, 20-keto and 11-hydroxy groups, 9-fluoro atom and 7-halogen group are important for the mediation of the activity. Again the presence of 6,7-unsaturation and a β -methyl group at C-16 position decreases the activity. This proves diagnostic potential of ETSA schemes in identifying the pharmacophoric fragments. The lipophilicity and molar refractivity parameters are also found to be important contributors to the activity.

It may be noted that the ETSA values of the common atoms of the compounds considered in the present study are available from the authors on request.

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